

TECHNOLOGY FOR OBTAINING DRY EXTRACT FROM SAFFRON PLANTING MATERIALS

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Annotation: The object of our research was the aboveground part of the spring primrose. To develop the optimal technology for obtaining a thick extract, the technological properties of medicinal plant raw materials were studied, an extracting, a method and conditions for the extraction process were selected. To determine the yield of the amount of flavonoids from the studied raw materials, the spectrophotometry method was used.

Keywords: extracted liquid, saffron requires, dynamic extraction methods

To obtain a dry extract of 10 kg, the collection of plants was crushed, sifted and loaded into a pre-prepared percolator. Ethyl alcohol was used as an extracting in various concentrations (20%, 40% and 70%), left to infuse for 24 hours. The resulting solution was heated to 50 ° C, left for 4 hours. Then the ultrasound was turned on for 10 minutes. The extracted liquid was transferred to a vacuum condenser and collector. It turned out 100 liters of liquid extract.

An additional process of our technological process in obtaining dry extract in production is the drying stage, which we carried out in the spray dryer "LPG-15 Spray dryer". The volume and sequence of work, as well as the specifics of a particular production, are most clearly displayed by technological schemes, which are an obligatory element of the industrial regulations for production.

In accordance with the extraction collection of plant raw materials was placed in a ceramic vessel, filled with a calculated volume of purified water (20 ° C) taking into account the absorption coefficient of raw materials; the raw materials were

heated with a gradual increase in temperature from 20 ° C to 40 ° C for 2 hours (at 1 ° C, every 6 minutes) and kept at a temperature of 40 ° C for an hour; after the specified time, subsequent heating was carried out with a gradual increase in temperature to 90 ° C for 8 hours (by 1 ° C, every 10 minutes) and kept at a temperature of 90 ° C for an hour; the vessel with vegetable raw materials was cooled for 10 hours with a gradual decrease in temperature from 90 ° C to 20 ° C (by 1 ° C every 9 minutes).

Most of the care of the plant and the entire process of collecting the stigma of saffron flowers is carried out manually, i.e. in a non-mechanized way. Therefore, this type of production is a very labor-intensive process involving a large number of workers both during plant care and harvesting. The production of 1 kg of saffron requires labor resources in the amount of 250-350 man-hours. This means that Tajikistan, where there is an excess of labor resources, and where labor costs are relatively low, has a certain advantage over, for example, Spain.

In addition, the organization of saffron production requires large investments. Most of the money needs to be spent on the purchase of planting material – about \$ 5.4 per kg. Approximately 0.6 kg of bulbs are planted per 1 m², and 6 tons of bulbs are obtained per 1 hectare. This means an investment of \$32,400 per hectare of plantation for planting material only. In addition, it is necessary to invest in technology, human resources and other production cycles, including pre-sale preparation and logistics. In general, the estimated return on investment in saffron production is 2.5 years.

In the course of our work, the following extraction methods were used: bismaceration, percolation and percolation. Bismaceration or repeated infusion of raw materials is widely used in pharmaceutical practice. By the nature of its flow, it can be attributed to static direct-flow periodic processes, when fresh extracting is fed to gradually depleted raw materials, the process proceeds in stages. Percolation and repercolation processes refer to dynamic extraction methods, which involves the

movement of the extracting relative to the raw material, in which the extracted substances are removed from the extraction zone or transferred to the next layers of the material.

The conducted studies allowed us to determine the optimal values of the parameters affecting the process of extracting biologically active substances from the primrose grass of spring. Among them are the shredding of raw materials, extractant, the ratio of raw materials and extractant, technological properties of medicinal plant raw materials.

In recent years, more and more attention has been paid to the search for new medicinal plants and the development of preparations from plant raw materials used in folk medicine. This is due to the possibility of their long-term use, complex effects on the body and the absence of side effects. One of the promising directions is the study of the antioxidant activity of medicinal plant raw materials, which is due to the presence of flavonoids, polyphenolic compounds and other groups of biologically active substances in it.

This region of the spectrum is sufficiently remote from the absorption spectra of accompanying phenolic and other organic substances contained in extracts from raw materials. As a comparison solution, we used the initial extraction solution without aluminum chloride, i.e. we used a differential version of spectrophotometry, which allows us to exclude the influence of concomitant substances on the analysis results. During the analysis, the samples were acidified with acetic acid to convert flavonoids and their accompanying substances into an dissociated form in order to improve the reproducibility of the results.

Optimal conditions have been selected and a method has been developed for quantifying the amount of flavonoids in a thick extract of spring primrose by spectrophotometric method. This technique can be used to standardize a thick extract of spring primrose herb in terms of the amount of flavonoids.

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